

Estimation of Trace Amounts of Protactinium in Thorium Nitrate Produced from Indian Monazite*

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A practical method has been developed to separate trace quantities of Pa from thorium nitrate sample produced from Indian Monazite Sand using (i) Dowex-50 for a quantitative separation of Pa or (ii) Dowex-1 to afford 80% recovery without any contamination of U in the sample.

By a repetition of the method it is possible to isolate radiochemically pure Pa without any contamination of U. This method can be adopted to prepare an absolute Pa source from uranium ore.

The ion-exchange method, described in this communication, can be adopted to prepare a standard Pa source from Indian Monazite Sand which contains 9.6% thorium oxide (ThO_2) and 0.37% uranium oxide (U_3O_8)¹. The separation technique described is of particular interest as Pa follows Th in normal chemical procedures.

The separation of Pa was effected from thorium nitrate sample using Dowex-50² and Dowex-1³ ion-exchange resins.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cation-exchange Method using Dowex-50.—A commercial thorium nitrate sample (1g.) in 1M-HNO₃ (25 ml) was passed at the rate of 0.5 ml/min. through a conditioned Dowex-50 resin (X-8, 50-100 mesh) kept over a piece of glass wool in a glass tube (dia. 1.1 cm and length 30 cm). The column was washed with 1M-HNO₃ (100 ml) and further with 50 ml of distilled water at the rate of 2.5 ml/min. Pa and Th were adsorbed on the resin column, but uranium appeared in the effluent. Thorium was eluted from the column with 1500 ml of 0.2M ammonium sulphate at the rate of 0.5 ml/min. at pH 3.4 till the last drop of the eluate failed to develop a red colour with thoronol reagent⁴. Protactinium was eluted from the column with 100 ml of 0.05M oxalic acid at pH 3.5⁵. The elution rate was kept at 0.5 ml/min. The column was washed with 100 ml of distilled water and the washings were also collected in the same manner.

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1. Gopinath *et al.*, "Activity Build-up of Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials" Part I, AEET/HP/Th/3, 1960.
2. Sullivan *et al.*, Proceedings of the International Conference on the Peaceful Uses of Atomic Energy, Vol. 7, p. 288, United States, New York, 1956.
3. Kraus *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 293.
4. Rødden, "Analytical Chemistry of Manhattan Project", McGraw Hill Book Company Inc., 1950.

The volume of the sample was reduced by evaporation and the solution made to 10 ml in a volumetric flask. The sample (0.5 ml) was taken on a stainless steel planchet, evaporated to dryness under an infrared lamp, flamed off over a Bunsen burner for 5 min., cooled, and counted in a low-background α -scintillation counter for α -activity.

Anion-exchange Method using Dowex-1.—A commercial thorium nitrate sample (1 g.) was taken in 8*M*-HCl (10 ml) and the solution was passed at the rate of 0.5 ml/min. through a conditioned Dowex-1 resin (X-8, 50-100 mesh), kept similarly as above. Both U and Pa were adsorbed on the column and thorium appeared in the effluent. The column was washed with 50 ml of 8*M*-HCl at the rate of 2.5 ml/min. till the effluent was free of thorium, as shown by the thoronol test⁴. Pa was eluted from the column with 25 ml of 3.8*M*-HCl. (At this concentration of HCl only Pa is eluted and no trace of U is desorbed from the column). The uranium was eluted from the column with 25 ml of 1 : 10 HClO₄ at 0.5 ml/min.

The eluate was evaporated to dryness and made to volume in a 10-ml volumetric flask. An aliquot (0.5 ml) was transferred to a 25-ml beaker and evaporated thrice to dryness with distilled water to eliminate HCl fumes. The subsequent procedure was the same as in the previous case.

The Pa sample was tested for U contamination by the fluorimetric method⁴. No trace of U was detected in the Pa fraction. The following table represents the Pa activity recovered, using Dowex-50 and Dowex-1 resins.

TABLE I
Counting data for Pa fraction.

Background of the counter = 6 counts/hr.
Efficiency of the counter (average) = 24.7%.

Sample No.	Dowex-50.	Dowex-1.
1	535.7 dpm	482 dpm.
2	534.0	490
3	536.4	475
4	..	481
Average	535.7	482

The resin from the column was then ashed at 700° and the ash was extracted with a few drops of water. The solution was then treated as usual for α -activity. No activity was noticed in the resin column.

DISCUSSION

In the manufacture of thorium nitrate, Pa follows Th as the hydroxide of Pa is carried by thorium hydroxide and Pa sulphate has low solubility⁶ in H₂SO₄ (conc.) and it might be expected to crystallise with thorium sulphate when present in ultra-trace quantities or ingrown into thorium sulphate.

5. Pillai, M. Sc. Thesis, University of Bombay, 1963.

6. "The Radiochemistry of Protactinium", NAS-NS 3016, p. 9, United States Atomic Energy Commission (December 1959).

The experimental values of Pa agree with calculated Pa content originally present in monazite. One g. of thorium nitrate produced from monazite sand provides 533.3 dpm α if equilibrium Pa is retained in the sample'. (Pa²³¹ grown into the thorium nitrate from β -decay of parent Th²³¹ only after radiochemical separation of Th is negligible). The total activity of Pa obtained from Dowex-50 and Dowex-1 is 535.7 and 482 dpm respectively. A quantitative recovery of Pa is obtained by the Dowex-50 method. The low recovery (80%) of Pa in the Dowex-1 method is due to incomplete elution. If elution is continued, there is contamination of U in the Pa eluate after five column volumes and the counting is not indicative of pure Pa activity.

The method indicates how a standard source of Pa²³¹ can be prepared from a uranium ore. Pa isotopes in the following chains present in the ore are treated as in equilibrium with their parent elements:

On separation of U and Pa as anionic chloro complexes by adsorption on the anion column, the isotopes adsorbed on the column from a uranium ore are:

Within ten minutes following adsorption, most of Pa²³⁴ decays to U²³⁴ and no fresh Pa²³⁴ grows in the column in the mean while due to the decay chain U²³⁸ $\rightarrow$ Th²³⁴ $\rightarrow$ Pa²³⁴. This is because its immediate precursor Th²³⁴ has a half-life of 24.1 days and U²³⁸ is very long lived. It has been calculated that growth of Pa²³⁴ is only 3% after 24 hr. of U separation. If the column is eluted with 3.8M-HCl, the only Pa isotope present will be Pa²³¹ along with traces of Pa²³⁴, which is only a β -emitted and decays completely in 10 min. The eluate is an isotopically pure solution of Pa²³¹. On calibration this can be used as a Pa standard source.

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